

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mulugeta****FIRST NAME: Addis****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Pr Cleenewerck****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on MacBook Air

PATH OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The approach of Euclid University with international students is different than other global universities. It breaks each course of studying into seven periods. After a careful reading and studying of each material, which is available as a Portable Document Format (PDF) and video, it is expected from students to write a Response Paper (RP). RPs are very important for students to summarize what they have acquired from their reading. The material of period one has a total of 83 Pages, which include the basic steps in writing an essay, introduction of an excellent paper, some rules of thumb for writing papers, Chicago Manual Style (CMS) and basic differences between American and British English. This clear path of essay writing helps students as a guideline to write an excellent research or dissertation work.

2) RULES OF WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

As I mentioned in the introduction, Euclid University has done a systematic breakdown of the course into seven periods. The 83 pages of the study material explains the deep art of writing an excellent academic essay. “Essay Writing: The Basics” starts with the “Basic Steps in Writing an Essay” and shows a detail information about an academic essay (EUCLID 2015, 2). The steps begin with “starting the essay, researching the topic, organising the ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay and editing the essay as well as handing the essay” (EUCLID 2015, 2-5). One of the important points in this section is that, testing the draft and structure of the essay. Any kind of academic research work has three main parts, introduction, main body and conclusion. According to the material, the introduction should start from general to specific. The main body,

however, it should answer the research questions by developing an argument and discussion. In this part of writing, researchers can use their knowledge, information from different sources by applying the rule of quotation to strengthen their discussion and argumentation. The last part of an academic writing is that, the conclusion. It should start with a specific and moves to general knowledge without adding additional new information (EUCLID 2015, 3).

In addition to that, the reading material in period one explains the use of style, definition and consequence of plagiarism. Plagiarism means that when a research writer takes any kind of information from other writers work as one's (EUCLID 2015, 8-12). It has a consequence and brings problem for future academic career. However, the material presents a solution how to solve this problem. It recommends that, if writers are using source of information from other writers, they must mention the source where it comes from, which is called "CITE."

Period one explains, when do we mention other writers in our research work, for example, "when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source" (EUCLID 2015, 11). "In-text citations and list of work cited" are the two types of citation (EUCLID 2015, 14). On the other hand, quotation and the idea of paraphrase the source of information are two ways of applying "in-text citation" (EUCLID 2015, 17). Using these two ways of citation for a research work, it has its own rules. In the material you can find the rules of citation very briefly, including "NOT to cite" (EUCLID 2015, 17-36). Furthermore, the use of American (US) or British (UK) footnote format is also valuable issue to show our readers, which English that we have used (EUCLID 2015, 34-40).

a) Rules of Thumb and Usage of America and British English

Worth mentioning in period one is that the "rules of Thumb for writing papers" The main points of "Rules of Thumb" are, "state the main thesis, stay focused, do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping such generalities as: write clearly, do not make the writing boring and clumsy, supporting assertions, take the views you are discussing seriously, when you finish writing, read your paper loud, how to use the first person singular, advice not using plagiarism" (EUCLID 2015, 41-43).

Further, period one shows also the basic differences and influences of change between American (US) and British (UK) English on writing academic essay. I had basic knowledge about using the US and UK English during my bachelor and master's thesis writing. However, through the year I have forgot some of these differences and its influence of change on writing academic essay. Studying period one, it refresh my knowledge in this regard and it gives me again deeper knowledge on the issue. Some of the basic difference between US and UK English, that are mentioned in this study material are, words same spelling but different pronunciation, same pronunciation but different spelling, same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation, same words but different or additional meanings, grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage,

same concept, different terms or expressions, same word, different in style, connotation and frequency (EUCLID 2015, 52-63). It is true that the material brings those students who are not native English speakers like me to the basics.

b) Chicago Manual of Style (CMS)

Period one discusses the meaning of style guide and why we need it for our academic writing. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as well as using American English for EUCLID students. The style guide is a vital instrument for research writers. From my reading, I found that, a style guide covers many different issues: preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layouts, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK vs. US) et cetera (EUCLID 2015, 50-51).

The study material puts also, “11 Important Reminders” and the use of comma in different situations (EUCLID 2015, 45). To join two independent clauses, use a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence modifier. Using commas to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, which are not essential to the sentence’s meaning. Not using commas to bracket phrases that are essential to a sentence’s meaning. When beginning a sentence with an introductory phrase or an introductory (dependent) clause, include a comma. On the other hand, the rules show that the use and function of apostrophe and punctuation. To indicate possession, end a singular noun with an apostrophe followed by an “s” otherwise, the noun’s form seems plural. Use proper punctuation to integrate a quotation into a sentence. If the introductory material is an independent clause, add the quotation after colon. If the introductory material ends in “thinks,” “saying,” or some other verb indicating expression, use a comma. It shows the possession, the proper use of “its” and “it’s,” the proper use of “your” and “you’re,” the difference between “that” and “which” et cetera (EUCLID 2015, 45-51).

Furthermore, the Chicago Style of formatting books and research papers (Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press), which is a completely new information for me. The CMS Crib Sheet contents has discussed very briefly about Chicago Style & Usage: (Abbreviations & Acronyms, Capitalization, Compound Words, Emphasis: Italics/Quotes, Numbers & Dates and Quotations). Chicago Page Formatting: (Title and Text Page, Footnotes, Headings & Lists, Bibliograph & Tables, Table Notes). Chicago End/Footnotes: (Authors & Books, Journals & Newspapers, Reports & Papers, References & Documents) (EUCLID 2015, 64-82).

3) CONCLUSION

During my two academic essay writings for my bachelor’s degree at the Addis Ababa University and for my master’s at the Wuerzburg-Schweinfurt Applied University in Germany, I have already applied and used some basic academic essay writing steps to

accomplish my degrees from both universities. Through reading this material to fulfill period one, I have acquired a deeper knowledge that will be very helpful and useful for my future dissertation work.

REFERENCE

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.